
GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Publishing Summary

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Publications

For manuscripts published from date range February 2021 - February 2026 (382)

Satarkar, G. S. (2026). Gendered and age-based barriers in access to inclusive higher education in India: A human rights perspective. Paper presented at the One-Day International Conference on Inclusive Higher Education as a Human Right: Addressing Gender, Age, and Intersectional Inequalities in Indian Universities, Centre for Women and Law, National Law University Odisha, in collaboration with the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC), Cuttack, India, January 31

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18417181

Civic Engagement & Administrative Advocacy Satarkar, G. S. (2023). Representation submitted to district authorities regarding road safety and traffic-control infrastructure for public transportation. Office of the District Collector and District Magistrate, Satara, Government of Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18359365

Public Policy & Administrative Representation Satarkar, G. S. (2023). Formal representation submitted to the Government of Maharashtra regarding reservation for the Maratha community. Divisional Commissioner's Office (General Administration Branch), Government of Maharashtra, Aurangabad, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18359339

Legal, Policy & Governance Engagement (RTI) Satarkar, G. S. (2024–2025). Applications and appellate proceedings under the Right to Information Act, 2005, concerning public administration, professional regulation, and examination transparency. Government of Maharashtra (Law and Judiciary Department; Maharashtra Medical Council) and Union Public Service Commission (UPSC), India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18359267

Legal & Research Engagement / RTI Matters Satarkar, G. S. (2024). First appeal under the Right to Information Act, 2005 (Reg. No. LAJDP/A/2024/60041). Office of the First Appellate Authority, Law and Judiciary Department, Government of Maharashtra, Mumbai, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18359250

Public Policy, Heritage & Administrative Advocacy Satarkar, G. S. (2023). Administrative representation and official correspondence regarding allotment of land for a public memorial of Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj. Sub-Divisional Officer's Office, Phaltan Sub-Division, District Satara, Government of Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18359411

Governance, Higher Education Policy & Transparency Engagement (RTI) Satarkar, G. S. (2025). Right to Information (RTI) application and official correspondence concerning internal assessment norms and academic progression policies in higher education. Secretariat of the Vice-President of India, New Delhi, India (application forwarded to the University of Delhi for further action)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18361175

Satarkar, G. S. (2026). Bridging Indian knowledge traditions and global pedagogical discourses: Reimagining teacher education in the light of NEP 2020. In Souvenir of the National Seminar on Reimagining Teacher and Teacher Education as per the Vision of National Education Policy 2020: Perspectives from Indian Knowledge Traditions to Global Discourses on Education (pp. xx-xx). Department of Education, School of Education, Central University of Jharkhand, Ranchi, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18361063

Public Policy & Social Justice Engagement Satarkar, G. S. (2023). Formal representation and administrative correspondence regarding reservation policy for the Maratha community. Divisional Commissioner's Office (General Administration Branch), Government of Maharashtra, Aurangabad, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18359427

Legal, Examination Policy & Transparency Engagement (RTI) Satarkar, G. S. (2025). Right to Information (RTI) application and official correspondence concerning evaluation procedures of descriptive examinations. Union Public Service Commission, New Delhi, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18359392

Satarkar, G. S. (2025). Certificate of appreciation. Zilla Parishad Primary School, Satara District, Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18359193

Satarkar, G. S. (2025). Certificate of Appreciation. Hind-Di-Chadar: 350th Shahidi Samagam. Minority Development Department, Government of Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18359127

Adv Satarkar, G. S. (2023–2025). Right to Information (RTI) applications and administrative representations before constitutional, parliamentary, and state authorities of India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18360361

Governance, Public Policy, and Transparency Engagement through the Right to Information Act, 2005 Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar, Advocate

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18360666

Governance, Transparency & Examination Policy Engagement (RTI) Satarkar, G. S. (2025). Right to Information (RTI) application and official response concerning evaluation procedures, answer-sheet disclosure, and assessment norms in competitive examinations. Union Public Service Commission, New Delhi, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

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Parliamentary Governance & Transparency Engagement (RTI) Satarkar, G. S. (2025). Right to Information (RTI) application seeking ministerial data and public disclosures, with inter-institutional transfer under the RTI Act, 2005. Lok Sabha Secretariat, Parliament of India, New Delhi, India (with transfers to the Election Commission of India and the Rajya Sabha Secretariat)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18360343

Satarkar, G. S. (2025). Right to Information (RTI) application and inter-institutional transfer concerning matters related to electoral administration. Rajya Sabha Secretariat, Parliament of

India, New Delhi, India (application transferred under Section 6(3) of the Right to Information Act, 2005, to the Election Commission of India)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18360288

Satarkar, G. S. (2024). Right to Information (RTI) application seeking information on the remuneration and allowances of the Prime Minister of India. Prime Minister's Office, New Delhi, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18360068

Intellectual Property, Governance & Transparency Engagement (RTI) Satarkar, G. S. (2025). Right to Information (RTI) application and official correspondence concerning registration and verification details of a Trade Mark Attorney under the Trade Marks Act, 1999. Intellectual Property India - Trade Marks Registry, Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Government of India, Mumbai, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18361087

Satarkar, G. S. (2025). Certificate of participation: 6th Dr. A. P. J. Abdul Kalam IPR Quiz Competition. Department for Promotion of Industry and Internal Trade (DPIIT) - IPR Chair & Centre for Intellectual Property Rights & Technology (CIPR&T), Damodaram Sanjivayya National Law University, Visakhapatnam, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18322277

Satarkar, G. S. (2026, January 21). Right to food as a human right in India: Legal framework, social accountability, and the road towards Viksit Bharat 2047. Paper presented at the One-Day National Seminar on Advancing Right to Food Security and Nutrition in India: Human Rights Perspective, Department of Law, Babasaheb Bhimrao Ambedkar University, Lucknow, India, in collaboration with the National Human Rights Commission (NHRC), India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18322363

Satarkar, G. S. (2026, January 21-22). Bridging Indian knowledge traditions and global pedagogical discourses: Reimagining teacher education in the light of NEP 2020. Paper presented at the Two-Day National Seminar on Reimagining Teacher and Teacher Education as per the Vision of National Education Policy 2020: Perspectives from Indian Knowledge Traditions to Global Discourses on Education, Department of Education, Central University of Jharkhand, Ranchi, India. Sponsored by ICSSR, ICWA, and MAKAIAS

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18322467

Satarkar, G. S. (2025, November 26). Invitation to participate in Constitution Day (Samvidhan Divas) academic programme on constitutional values and social equality [Official invitation]. Maharashtra State Students' Association, Central University of Haryana, Mahendragarh, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18296161

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, October 17). Certificate of participation in the one-day national webinar on "Public Relations during COVID-19". Department of Journalism and Mass Communication, Mandasaur University, in collaboration with Public Relations Society of India (PRSI), Bhopal Chapter, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18288851

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, September 20). Certificate of participation in the national-level webinar on "Himalayan Trekking Expedition - An Adventure". Deogiri Institute of Engineering and Management Studies (DIEMS), Aurangabad, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18288867

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, September 29). Certificate of participation in the webinar on "Role of Material Properties in Defence". Department of Aeronautical Engineering, Nehru Institute of Engineering and Technology, Coimbatore, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18288872

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, September 30). Certificate of participation in the one-day international webinar on "Role of Science and Technology during COVID-19 Pandemic: A Perspective Analysis". Department of Science and IQAC, Mayanguri College, West Bengal, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18289132

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, September 25-26). Certificate of participation in the workshop "Google Forms & generating certificates: A hands-on online academic program". Department of Humanities and Sciences, Balaji Institute of Technology & Science, Narsampet, Warangal Rural, Telangana, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18288881

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, September 11-16). Certificate of participation in the 7th National Webinar Series on "Media trials & constitutionalism: An Indian perspective". KLE College of Law, Kalamboli, Navi Mumbai, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18288910

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, September 11-16). Certificate of participation in the 7th National Webinar Series on "Media Trials & Constitutionalism: An Indian Perspective". KLE Society's KLE College of Law, Kalamboli, Navi Mumbai, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18288921

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, September 14). Certificate of participation in the webinar on "Fundamentals of Contract Drafting". KLE Society's KLE College of Law, Kalamboli, Navi Mumbai, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18288933

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, October 12). Certificate of participation in the National Level Webinar on New National Education Policy 2020. Prof. Sambhajirao Kadam College, Deur (Arts, Commerce, Science & Community College), Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18288947

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, September 25–26). Certificate of participation in the webinar "E-Content: Need of the Hour in COVID-19 Pandemic". Gyan Vihar School of Education, Suresh Gyan Vihar University (Accredited by NAAC with A+ Grade), Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18289038

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, September 26). Certificate of participation in the one-day webinar "Earth Observation Satellites for Social, Environmental and Economic Studies". Shri Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18289056

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, September 28–30). Certificate of participation in the three-day webinar on "Managing Literature for Scholarly Writing". Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC), Mar Athanasius College

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18289151

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, October 3). Certificate of participation in the webinar "Biodiversity and Environment Conservation". Department of Zoology, Balwant College, Vita, Dist. Sangli, Maharashtra, India

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Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18289080

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, October 18). E-certificate of participation in the state-level webinar "Relevance of Gandhian Theories in Contemporary Period". NSS Unit-V and Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC), Maynaguri College, University of North Bengal, West Bengal, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18289101

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, September 20). Certificate of participation in the international webinar "Innovative Data Analytics Tools for Chemical and Life Sciences Research". Department of Chemical Society, Ranchi, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18289115

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, September 7-11). Certificate of participation in the five-day online faculty development programme on "Climate Change and Environment: Legal Protection" (UGC-STRIDE Project). Department of Law, School of Legal Studies, Central University of Tamil Nadu, in association with Shivaji University

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18289161

Satarkar, G. N. (2020, July 27). Blockchain use cases. Amity Future Academy. Satarkar, G. N. (2020, July 27). Scripting for hackers. Amity Future Academy. Satarkar, G. N. (2020, July 14). Search engine marketing. Amity Future Academy. Satarkar, G. N. (2020, July 14). Blockchain technology and management. Amity Future Academy. Satarkar, G. N. (2020, July 14). Introduction to product management. Amity Future Academy. Satarkar, G. N. (2020, July 13). Basics of Java. Amity Future Academy

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18290510

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 12). Finance quiz [Certificate of participation]. Department of Management Studies, Rajalakshmi Engineering College (Autonomous), Chennai, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18290218

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Internet of things (IoT) [Certificate of participation]. Sri Eshwar College of Engineering, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18290329

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in the international webinar on "Post-Covid global economy: A rethink on strategies and policy". Department of Economics, University of North Bengal, India. (August 27-28, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18287048

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Certificate of participation in the five-day TEQIP-III sponsored workshop on "Emerging trends in nanotechnology (ETNT-2020)". Rajasthan Technical University, Kota, in collaboration with Jaipur Engineering College and Research Centre, Jaipur, India. (September 21-25, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18288622

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Certificate of participation in a one-day national-level online student development programme on "Soft Skills for Personality Development". Department of English, Government Ram Bhajan Rai NES P.G. College, Jaspurnagar, Chhattisgarh, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18288697

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in a one-day national-level webinar on "I-STEM: A gateway for researchers stepping towards Aatmanirbhar Bharat". Faculty of Humanities and Science, Dr. M.G.R. Educational and Research Institute (Deemed to be University), Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India. (August 25, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18286659

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in an AICTE-sponsored five-day virtual short-term training programme (STTP) on "Industry 4.0". Nitte Meenakshi Institute of Technology, Bengaluru, Karnataka, India, in association with AICTE. (August 24-28, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18286698

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in a two-day research methodology and post-capacity building programme on law. PDP's Law College, Phaltan (Shivaji University, Kolhapur), in collaboration with S. S. Khanna Girls' Degree College, University of Allahabad, Prayagraj, and District Legal Services Authority, Allahabad (Prayagraj), India. (August 22-September 4, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18286442

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in a national-level six-day faculty development programme on "Imparting soft skills and life skills for success". Department of English (Post Graduate), Shanti Devi Arya Mahila College, Dinanagar, Gurdaspur, Punjab, India (NAAC re-accredited with 'A' grade; College with Potential for Excellence by UGC). (August 17-22, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18286515

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in an international webinar on "Current trends in next generation gene sequencing". Faculty of Pharmacy, Dr. M.G.R. Educational and Research Institute (Deemed to be University), Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India. (August 31, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18286730

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in a five-day online national lecture series on differential paradigms of education. Department of Education, Crizzily College of Education, affiliated to Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU), in collaboration with Law College Phaltan, India. (August 24–28, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18286537

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in a one-week faculty development programme on "Advances in water resources management and sustainable environment". Department of Civil Engineering, M.S. Ramaiah Institute of Technology (Autonomous, affiliated to VTU), Bengaluru, India, sponsored by AICTE and organized in association with IQAC-MSRIT. (August 17–21, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18286800

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in a one-day national webinar on "New Education Policy 2020 and challenges". Academic Excellence Committee, Shri Dadashheb Gawai Charitable Trust's Amravati, Maharashtra, India. (August 24, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18286874

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in a one-day national webinar on "Yoga for immunity with respect to the current scenario". Department of Physical Education and Arts Commerce College, Yoda, Maharashtra, India. (August 29, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18286845

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in a national-level quiz on "Strength of materials and structural analysis". Department of Civil Engineering, Chaitanya (Deemed to be University), Telangana, India. (August 29–30, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18286883

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in an AICTE-sponsored six-day short-term training programme on recent advances in tribology and surface engineering. Department of Mechanical Engineering, Saintgits College of Engineering (Autonomous), Kottayam, Kerala, India. (August 17–22, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18286920

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in an international webinar on "The leadership impact". ThickNess Learning Community, India. (September 6, 2020)

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Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18286931

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in a state-level webinar on "National Education Policy-2020". Dyandeep Prabodhini's Zep Academy, Gadhinglaj, in collaboration with Vidya Prasarak Mandal, Gadhinglaj, Dr. Ghali College, Gadhinglaj, and Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India. (August 30, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18286969

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in a national webinar on "Literature in translation: Issues and challenges". Arts, Commerce & Science College, Nashik, affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, Maharashtra, India. (September 10, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18286987

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in a one-day national webinar on "Impact of COVID-19 on academic library services". IQAC, Library and Department of Library & Information Science, Sambhajirao Kendre Mahavidyalaya, Jalkot, approved by Swami Ramanand Teerth Marathwada University, Nanded, Maharashtra, India. (September 7, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18287007

Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in "C5: Crash course on climate change and its consequences". Department of Biotechnology and Medical Engineering, National Institute of Technology Rourkela, Odisha, India, in association with Unnat Bharat Abhiyan (RCI Odisha) and Genesys. (October 10, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in an international webinar on "Veda for world peace". Organized by Prof. Yogesh Mandapati, Secretary, M.S.Y.V.P., with participation of international scholars including Prof. Dev Prasad Tripathi (Vice-Chancellor, M.S.Y.V.P.), Prof. Upendra Pashupati (Secretary, M.S.Y.V.P.), and Dr. Josse Luis Alvarez Roser (Director - NIVC, Vietnam). (September 10, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18288155

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, September 24). Certificate of participation in a one-day national webinar on "Challenges before Indian Politics in Covid-19 & Thereafter". Department of Political Science, Janvikas Mahavidyalaya, Bansarola, Maharashtra, India

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18288722

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, September 27). Certificate of participation in the webinar "Travel, culture and society: Opportunities and reflections" (Student Development Programme, Webinar Series-11). Department of Sociology and Social Work, GEMS Arts and Science College, Malappuram, Kerala, India (via Google Meet)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18288778

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, September 5). Certificate of participation in the online event "Teacher's Day Speak Out Contest". National Service Scheme (NSS) and National Cadet Corps (NCC), Law College Phaltan, Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18288827

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, September 26). Certificate of participation in the online webinar on "Analysing Critical Factors Affecting Learning Environment in Higher Institutions". Centre for Capacity Building Programmes for School Teachers, Tamil Nadu Teachers Education University, Chennai, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18288834

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, September 27). Certificate of participation in the national webinar entitled "Understanding the Dynamics and Dimensions of the Ongoing Stand-off between India and China". Department of Political Science, Law College Phaltan, in collaboration with Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC), Mohanpur, West Tripura, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18288843

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, September 6). Certificate of participation in the one-day national webinar on "21st Century Hindi Literature: Women Discourse" (इक्कीसवीं सदी के हिंदी साहित्य में सत्री विमर्श). Organized by the Department of Hindi, Mahatma Jyotiba Phule Mahavidyalaya, Mumbai, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18289207

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, October 3). Certificate of participation in the one-day webinar on "Redefining Strategies and Executive Innovative Approaches for Business & HR during COVID-19 and Post-COVID". Balaji Institute of Management Sciences (Affiliated to INTU (H), Approved by AICTE), Narsampet, Warangal Rural, Telangana, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

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Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, September 26). Certificate of participation in the National Webinar on NEP-2020: Highlights and implications for higher education. Mar Athanasius College (Autonomous), Kothamangalam, Kerala, India, in collaboration with the Centre for Educational and Social Studies (CESS)

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Arihant Institute of Business Management (AIBM) and Arihant College of Arts, Commerce & Science (ACACS), Pune, India

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Central University of Haryana. (2025, April 17). Letter of recommendation for summer internship of Ganesh Shrirang Nale Satarkar (Department of Sociology). Mahendergarh, Haryana, India

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Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in the international virtual faculty development programme on "Sustainable development and research opportunities in food and chemical engineering". Departments of Food Technology and Chemical Engineering, Hindusthan College of Engineering and Technology, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India. (October 5-11, 2020)

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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 26). Participation in an international virtual seminar on "Career Awareness & Job Opportunities in India and Overseas". Government P. G. College, Bina (M.P.), India, under the Swami Vivekananda Career Guidance Scheme
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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 25). Chanakya Neeti: The mantra to excel (National webinar). Departments of Economics and History, Pillai HOC College of Arts, Science & Commerce, in association with the Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC)
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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 30–31). Participation in a national webinar on "Contribution of Physics towards Atma Nirbhar Bharat (CPTANB-2020)". Department of Physics, N. S. C. B. Government P. G. College, Biaora, Rajgarh, Madhya Pradesh, India, in association with IAPT (RC-09) and MPHEQP World Bank Project

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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 23). Novel strategies against multidrug resistant cancers. International webinar organized by Raj Kumar Goel Institute of Technology (Pharmacy), approved by AICTE and PCI, with the UG programme accredited by the National Board of Accreditation (NBA)

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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 21). Advancements and applications of nanotechnology in targeting inflammatory diseases (International webinar). Raj Kumar Goel Institute of Technology (Pharmacy)

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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 13–18). Applications of mathematical sciences (One-week online short-term training programme). Department of Basic Sciences and Humanities, K.D.K. College of Engineering, Nagpur, in association with the Indian Society for Technical Education (ISTE), New Delhi, India

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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 10–12). United by pens, divided by fence: Perspectives on partition literature (Three-day international webinar). Department of English, Netaji Subhash Mahavidyalaya, Udaipur, Gomati, Tripura, India

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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, August 24). Participation in a one-day state-level webinar on "Marathi Literature and Contemporary Issues". Department of Marathi, D. B. D. Handewadi Mahavidyalaya, Aundh, Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 20). How to submit a winning project proposal (Webinar). Internal Quality Assurance Cells of St. Joseph's College (Autonomous), Irinjalakuda, Thrissur, Kerala, and Morning Star Home Science College, Angamaly, Ernakulam, Kerala, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 21–23). Sharing on social science, education and technology (International expert session). Faculty of Teachers Training and Education, Universitas Muhammadiyah Sidenreng Rappang

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 29–30). Forensic entomology and its relevance in legal proceedings (International webinar). Department of Zoology, University of Lucknow
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 3–4). Advances in agricultural biotechnology (International webinar). Department of Agriculture Science, AKS University
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18280926

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 29). Impact of lockdown due to COVID-19 on forest and environment in India (National webinar). Department of Forestry, Government Kaktiya PG College, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18280909

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 5). Enhancing quality culture in technical institutes through online teaching for outcome-based education (Webinar). All India Shri Shivaji Memorial Society's College of Engineering, Pune, in association with The Institution of Engineers (India), Kolkata, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18280894

Ganesh Shirang Satarkar. Cyber Security and Artificial Intelligence in the Digital Age: Legal, Ethical, and Societal Perspectives. Book of Abstracts, National Conference, Shyam Lal College, University of Delhi, 2026, pp. 34–35
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 2). Cloud security: Common vulnerabilities and ways to address them (Webinar). Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, St. Joseph's Institute of Technology, Chennai, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18280883

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, August 1). Participation in an online national conference. Department of Culture, Krishna Mahavidyalaya, Rethare (Bk.), Maharashtra, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18282972

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 10–12). United by pens, divided by fence: Perspectives on partition literature. Three-day international webinar organized by the Department of English, Netaji Subhas Mahavidyalaya, and streamed live via YouTube with active participation in discussions
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 21). Confidence and technology enabled teacher – Part I (One-day national-level web workshop). Mangalore University Commerce Teachers Association (MUCTA)
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 6). COVID-19: Global economic challenges and opportunities (International webinar). Department of Business Administration and Department of Information Management System, Shree Chandrababhu Jain College (Affiliated to the University of Madras), Minjur, Tamil Nadu, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18277590

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 22–23). Fishery business ecosystem in India (Two-day webinar). Centre for Agricultural Market Intelligence, National Agricultural Higher Education Project (NAHEP-CAAST), Anand Agricultural University, Anand, Gujarat, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18277639

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 24–25). Post-COVID-19 environmentalism: Possible futures (International webinar). Department of English & Political Science, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar College, Betai, Nadia, West Bengal, India (supported by IQAC)
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 5). How to become a data scientist (Webinar). Organized by BHAIDI and delivered by Utsav Aggarwal, Senior Data Scientist, Oracle; streamed on YouTube
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18277577

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 6). Career in travel and tourism industry post COVID-19 (Webinar). Indore Management Institute and Research Centre, Indore, Madhya Pradesh, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18281047

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 8). Readiness of universities and institutions for the new revolutionary changes in the education system. Live webinar organized by Ambika Ram Devi Degree College, under the Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18281027

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 25). Chanakya Neeti: The mantra to excel (National webinar). Departments of Economics and History, Pillai HOC College of Arts, Science & Commerce, in association with the Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC)
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 2). Emotional intelligence (One-day webinar). Faculty of Management Studies, AKS University, Satna, Madhya Pradesh, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 13–17). Road map to hybrid research (Five-day Faculty Development Programme). Department of Biotechnology, Dr. M. G. R. Educational and Research Institute (Deemed to be University), Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18277654

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 10–11). Lessons from the past: Studying trends and responses to epidemics (Two-day national webinar). Department of History, Sophia Girls' College (Autonomous), Ajmer, Rajasthan, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18277563

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, August 3–9). Participation in a national level faculty development programme on "Innovations in Biotechnology as Life-Saving Prospective". Department of Biotechnology (CHRD) and Department of Biotechnology (FASH), in collaboration with the Karpagam Academy of Higher Education, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18283153

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, August 3). Participation in an international webinar on "Microbial Ecology of the Human Skin: From Immunity to Infection". PG and Research Department of Zoology, Chikkaiah Naicker College, Erode, Tamil Nadu, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18283081

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, August 2). Participation in an online quiz on "COVID-19 Pandemic". C. G. Bhakta Institute of Biotechnology (CGBIT), Uka Tarsadia University, Maliba Campus, Bardoli, Gujarat, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, August 2). Participation in a one-day state-level workshop on "Anapan and Vipassana Meditation". Department of Mass Communication and Journalism, Shri Shivaji College, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Participation in a two-day online national seminar on Role of Basic Science and Biotechnology in Mitigating COVID-19 Pandemic. J. M. Patel Arts, Commerce and Science College, Bhandara, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 22). COVID-19 pandemic general awareness quiz (Online quiz and public health awareness activity). Internal Quality Assurance Cell and Department of Physics, Rajarshi Shahu Arts, Commerce and Science College

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18281239

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 17). Innovative product design using Arduino (Live online workshop). Atal Incubation Centre, Pondicherry Engineering College Foundation

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18281033

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 28). Participation in a one-day national level webinar on "Atmanirbhar Bharat: An Elixir of the Indian Economy". Department of Commerce, Shri S. R. Kanthi Arts, Commerce and Science College, Mudhol, Bagalkot, Karnataka, India (IQAC initiative)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18283121

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 17). Biology of COVID-19 and administrative efforts to control it (National webinar). Department of Political Science, Meerut College, Meerut

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Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18281266

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 15–19). Rejuvenation of body, mind, and soul (Online faculty development programme). Department of Physical Education, Ethiraj College for Women (Autonomous), Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18277689

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 21). Importance of physics in industry and opportunities for physics students (Webinar). Department of Physics, People's Education Society's Milind College of Science

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18281147

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 13–19). Recent trends in management (Seven-day online faculty development programme). Department of Management Studies, Gates Institute of Technology, Shivaji University, Kolhapur

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18281076

Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 30). Qualitative research (Online webinar). Department of Psychology, Avinashilingam Institute for Home Science and Higher Education for Women, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18277625

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in the international webinar "Strengthening the immune system against COVID-19 through agricultural innovations". College of Agriculture, Sri Karan Narendra Agriculture University, Fatehpur-Shekhawati, Sikar, Rajasthan, India (July 29, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18268374

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in the webinar "Challenges and opportunities for engineers in electric vehicle design and development". Department of Robotics and Automation, Faculty of Engineering and Technology, Jain (Deemed-to-be University), Bengaluru, India (August 7, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18268463

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Completion of a one-week online short-term training programme on teaching learning pedagogies. Department of Mechanical Engineering, A. G. Patil Polytechnic Institute, Solapur, Maharashtra, India, under the Quality Improvement Scheme (AQIS), All India Council for Technical Education (AICTE), New Delhi (August 3–8, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18268501

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in a one-day state-level online workshop on management of stress with anapan and vipassana meditation. Department of Mass Communication and Journalism, Shri Shivaji College, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India (August 2, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18268591

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in a one-day national webinar on pre- and post-corona pandemic conditions of migrated labour in India. Department of Commerce in collaboration with IQAC, Yashwantrao Chawhan Arts, Commerce and Science College, Lakhandur, Maharashtra, India, and Adv. Vitthalrao Banpurkar Memorial Arts and Commerce College, Malewada, Maharashtra, India (July 29, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18268597

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in a two-day national level webinar on developing effective writing and speaking skills. Department of Humanities and Sciences, BIT Institute of Technology-Hindupur, Andhra Pradesh, India (August 5-6, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18268613

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in a one-week national online faculty development programme on advanced welding technologies. Department of Mechanical Engineering, Jain (Deemed-to-be University), Bengaluru, India (August 4-8, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18268623

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in a one-day national webinar on NAAC revised accreditation guidelines and role of IQAC in post-COVID-19 era. Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC), St. Vincent Pallotti College of Engineering and Technology, Nagpur, Maharashtra, India (August 6, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18268730

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in the web session "A tale of two Indias: Are the best leaving behind the rest?". Department of Economics, University of Allahabad, India (July 30, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18268821

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in the workshop "Enhancing fitness and athletics science". Department of Physical Education and Sports, Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, Maharashtra, India (August 6-7, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18268855

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in a one-week online faculty development program on optimization techniques for mechanical engineers. Department of Mechanical Engineering, Vignan Institute of Technology and Science, Hyderabad, Telangana, India (July 27-August 1, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18269030

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in a six-day national webinar on present status and prospects of food technology. Sau. K. S. K. (Kaku) College of Food Technology and College of Agriculture, Beed, Maharashtra, India (July 24-29, 2020)

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Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in the national webinar on national education policy, autonomy status: Challenges and opportunities. IQAC and Department of Political Science, Rani Parvati Devi College of Arts and Commerce, Belagavi, Karnataka, India (August 8, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18269101

Satarkar, Ganesh Shrirang Nale. (2020). International conference participation: Emerging trends in healthcare technology in the post-COVID-19 era. Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur, India

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Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in the national webinar on emerging trends of techno skills in education. Department of Education, St. Thomas College, Bhilai, Chhattisgarh, India (July 31, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18268987

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in the international webinar on work culture in changing times. Department of Commerce, Mahatma Gandhi Central University, Bihar, India, in association with the University of Guadalajara, Mexico (August 4, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18268958

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in a five-day online faculty development programme on recent trends in applicable mathematics. Department of Mathematics, Karunya Institute of Technology and Sciences, Coimbatore, Tamil Nadu, India (July 27–31, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18268436

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in a two-day online national seminar on role of basic science and biotechnology in mitigating the COVID-19 pandemic. J. M. Patel Arts, Commerce and Science College, Bhandara, Maharashtra, India, in collaboration with Rajiv Gandhi Biotechnology Centre, Rashtrasant Tukadoji Maharaj Nagpur University (July 29–30, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18269045

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in a one-day national webinar on impact of COVID-19 pandemic on Indian agriculture and rural livelihoods. Department of Geography and Economics, Government College Mandipur, District Ujjain, Madhya Pradesh, India, under the MPHEQIP-World Bank Scheme (July 28, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in a two-day national webinar on "An insight in NAAC revised guidelines". Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC), K.L.E. Society's G. I. Bagewadi Arts, Science & Commerce College, Nipani, Karnataka, India

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Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in the webinar "Health: The most important investment you need to make now". IEEE NCU StartHub, The NorthCap University, Gurugram, India (July 22, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

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Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in one-week online faculty development program on nanoscience and nanotechnology: Current perspectives. Department of Physics and Department of Mechanical Engineering, G. H. Rasoni College of Engineering, Nagpur, India, in association with The Institution of Engineers (India), Nagpur Local Centre (July 27–August 1, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18268285

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in the webinar "IT network infrastructure: An overview". Sri Eshwar College of Engineering, Coimbatore, India (August 5, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Participation in the international webinar on open educational resources and Google site creation. DMI-St. John the Baptist University, Republic of Malawi, Central Africa (July 27–28, 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Introduction to product management (Professional certification). Amity Future Academy, India

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Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Emerging respiratory viruses, including COVID-19: Methods for detection, prevention, response and control (WHO online course). World Health Organization
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18252965

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Certificate of achievement for successful completion of International Level Online Quiz on "Power Generation Technologies" (Score: 20%). Department of Mechanical Engineering, O. P. Jindal University, Raigarh, Chhattisgarh, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18258813

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Certificate of participation and achievement (100%) in National Level Technical E-Quiz on "Communications". Department of Electronics and Communication Engineering, Sanketika Institute of Technology & Management, Visakhapatnam, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18258750

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Certificate of participation and successful completion of National Level E-Quiz on "Immunology and Immunotechnology". Department of Microbiology, Justice Basheer Ahmed Sayeed College for Women, Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18258851

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Certificate of participation and successful completion of National Level E-Quiz 2020 on "Commerce Aptitude Test" (Score: 40%). Department of Commerce, Brahmanand College, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18258890

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Certificate of participation and excellence in COVID-19 Online National Awareness Quiz Competition (Score: 64%). Shri Narendra Tidke College of Arts and Commerce, Ramtek, Nagpur District, Maharashtra, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
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Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Certificate of participation in online science quiz on "E-Waste Management". Department of Chemistry, Shankarrao Chavan Mahavidyalaya, Ardhapur, Nanded, Maharashtra, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, July 18). Content marketing (Professional certificate). Amity Future Academy, India

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18252912

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Certificate of participation in quiz "A Bibliophiles Paradise: A Quiz for Every Book Lover" (Score: 40%). Central Library, Agnel Institute of Technology and Design, Assagao, Goa, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18258913

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, October 26–31). Harmony in the workplace: Effective interpersonal and communication skills (Phase I: Communication skills @ workplace). One-week AICTE-sponsored Short Term Training Programme, Department of Sciences & Humanities, Sri Venkateswara Engineering College, Tirupati, Andhra Pradesh, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18252416

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Certificate of participation in National Level E-Quiz on "Commerce Aptitude Test" (Score: 40%). Department of Commerce, Brahmanand College, Kanpur, Uttar Pradesh, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18258928

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Certificate of participation in International Online Conference on "Emerging Trends in Healthcare Technology in Post-COVID-19 Era". SPARC Cell & School of Medical Science and Technology, Indian Institute of Technology Kharagpur, West Bengal, India (8–9 August 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18259035

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Certificate of participation in National Webinar on "Sustenance of Physics During Pandemic". Department of Physics, Government Rajeev Lochan PG College, Rajim, Chhattisgarh, India (13–14 August 2020)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Certificate of participation in International Online Webinar on "Entrepreneurship During COVID-19". IILM Academy of Higher Learning, Lucknow, India (12 August 2020)

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Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, November 9–21). Formal modeling, control, and real-time implementation of cyber-physical systems (Phase II). Two-week AICTE-sponsored online Faculty Development Programme, Department of Electrical & Electronics Engineering, V.S.B. Engineering College, Karur, Tamil Nadu, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Certificate of appreciation for excellent performance in the online COVID-19 pandemic general awareness quiz. Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC), Sadguru Gadage Maharaj College, Karad, Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18252311

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020, July 14). Professional certificate in search engine marketing. Amity Future Academy, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18252352

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Professional certificate in mobile app marketing. Amity Future Academy, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18252388

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Successful completion of the COVID-19 awareness quiz organized in association with the Department of Biotechnology and Department of Zoology. St. Joseph's College (Autonomous), Irinjalakuda, Kerala, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18252430

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Marketing management (National-level online quiz; score: 48%). Department of Commerce, Government Degree College, Mandapeta, East Godavari District, Andhra Pradesh, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18252507

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Modules for learners' online engagement (Online national-level FDP). D. Y. Patil Institute of Management Studies, Pune, Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18252555

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Big-data analytics and cyber security in smart grid monitoring and control. AICTE-sponsored STTP, Knowledge Institute of Technology, Salem, Tamil Nadu, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18252621

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Company secretary executive entrance test (CSEET)—Pass. Institute of Company Secretaries of India (ICSI), New Delhi, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18252686

Satarkar, G. S. (2022). Interplay of law and economics in the contemporary world (Masterclass course). Centre for Law, Economics and Competition Policy, Jagan Nath University, Jaipur, Rajasthan, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18252772

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2020). Basics of Java. Professional certification course, Amity Future Academy, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18252890

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 12). Q-Fiesta for biochemist-2020. Online E-Quiz organized by the Department of Biochemistry, Vivekanandha College of Arts and Sciences for Women (Autonomous), Tiruchengode, Namakkal District, Tamil Nadu, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18240895

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, August 22–23). Shri Ram ke vibhinna aayam: Valmiki–Tulsi se nirala aur anya sahitya mein Shri Ram ki drishti aur arth. Two-day international seminar, Bharatiya Bhasha Parishad, Kolkata, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239269

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, August 25). Rights of women at workplace with special reference to the Sexual Harassment of Women at Workplace (Prevention, Prohibition and Redressal) Act, 2013. Participation in the 6th National Webinar Series organized by KLE College of Law, Kalamboli, Navi Mumbai, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239279

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, August 27). Cyber laws: Rights and future challenges. Webinar conducted as part of the 6th National Webinar Series organized by KLE College of Law, Kalamboli, Navi Mumbai, Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239756

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, August 28). Application and tools in next generation sequencing (NGS) data analysis. Webinar organized by the Department of Science, School of Arts, Science and Commerce, and Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC), Rai University, Ahmedabad, Gujarat, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239567

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, August 23). National Educational Policy–2020. One-day national webinar jointly organized by Shivaji University, Kolhapur, and Shree Ravalnath Co-operative Housing Finance Society Ltd., Ajara (Multi-State), Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239633

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Impact and strategies for higher education: Comprehensive research pedagogy, methodology, and design. Certificate of completion, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Institute of Technology, Jalandhar (TEQIP-III)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239370

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, August 17–22). Recent advances in tribology and surface engineering: Series I—Introduction to tribology and surface engineering. AICTE-sponsored six-day (one-week) online short-term training programme organized by the Department of Mechanical Engineering, Saintgits College of Engineering (Autonomous), Kottayam, Kerala, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239605

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, August 19–20). Current trends in chemical process technology and materials development. Indo-UK joint international webinar jointly organized by the Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati, Assam, India, and the University of Aberdeen, Scotland, United Kingdom

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239732

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 9). Engineering project management: Scope, cost, risk and teams. International webinar organized by the Department of Mechanical Engineering, Francis Xavier Engineering College (Autonomous, NBA Accredited), Tirunelveli, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18240701

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Building a live video channel with MediaLive and MediaPackage. Online course completed on June 29, 2020 (20 minutes). AWS Training and Certification

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18240657

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 27). Tulsi ke Ram aur Ram ke Tulsi [Tulsi's Ram and Ram's Tulsi]. International webinar organized by Ramayan Kendra, Bhopal, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18240151

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, August 28). Beyond the boundaries: Saga of burgeoning urban, eroded coasts and sustainability. One-day national webinar organized by the Post-Graduate Department of Geography, Fakir Mohan University, Balasore, Odisha, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239543

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, August 29–30). Strength of materials & structural analysis. Certificate of appreciation for successful completion of an online national-level quiz organized by the Department of Civil Engineering, Chaitanya (Deemed to be University), Hanamkonda, Warangal, Telangana, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239645

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 20). Past, present and future trends in vaccinology. International webinar organized by Madurai Kamaraj University, Madurai, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18240175

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 3). Flexible learning principles in distance education. Webinar-workshop organized by empowerED Advocacy, conducted online (1.5 hours)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18240090

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, August 8). Optimal health & fitness (Speaker: Vikash Kumar). International webinar, Asian Development Educational & Research Foundation (ADERF), India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239415

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 10). Python programming and its applications. Webinar organized by Pantech e-Learning (Online Learning Platform), India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18240634

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 20–27). Four-day soft skills online training programme. Organized by Krantiguru Shyamji Krishna Verma Kachchh University, Bhuj-Kachchh, Gujarat, India, in collaboration with Business Excellence Inc., USA

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239615

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 27–31). Emerging technologies for sustainable universe. Five-day National Level Faculty Development Programme organized by SEEK, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18240201

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 3). Labour market need assessment for demand-driven TVET. Webinar organized by the Colombo Plan Staff College (CPSC), Manila, Philippines
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239812

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, September 3). Seekhne ke liye sarvottam vatavaran evam chhatron ka sahyog: Rashtriya Shiksha Neeti 2020 ke sandarbh mein [Best learning environment and student cooperation in the context of National Education Policy 2020]. National webinar organized by Government P.G. College, Hamirpur, Uttar Pradesh, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239292

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 7). Investigation of the effect of cracks on vibration parameters of a cantilever beam. Webinar organized by Francis Xavier Engineering College (Autonomous), accredited by NBA, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239855

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, September 10). Literature in translation: Issues and challenges. One-day national webinar organized by IQAC and Language Faculty, K. V. N. Naik Shikshan Prasarak Sanstha's Arts, Commerce & Science College, Nashik, affiliated to Savitribai Phule Pune University, Pune, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239318

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 23). Identifying research gap: Problems and solutions. International webinar conducted as part of a hybrid webinar series on Innovative and emerging technology in the field of research, organized by the Research Cell, Shah & Anchor Kutchhi Engineering College, University of Mumbai, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239868

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 15). The importance of eco-criticism in literature. National webinar organized by the Department of English, Shree Chandraprabhu Jain College, Minjur, Tamil Nadu, India (affiliated to the University of Madras)
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239904

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 8). Readiness of universities and institutions for the new revolutionary changes in the education system. Live webinar organized by Ambika Ram Devi Degree College, Ramna Taufir, Harriya, Basti, Uttar Pradesh, India (IQAC)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239880

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 25). Chanakya Neeti: The mantra to excel. National webinar organized by the Departments of Economics and History in association with the Internal Quality Assurance Cell (IQAC), Pillai HOC College of Arts, Science & Commerce, Rasayani, Maharashtra, India (accredited by NAAC)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18240024

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 18). Certificate of dedication for COVID-19 awareness and community service. Awarded by the Rural Urban Council of Skills & Vocational Studies (RUSVS), New Delhi, India, for contribution to COVID-19 prevention awareness in accordance with World Health Organization (WHO) guidelines

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239783

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 29). Impact of lockdown due to COVID-19 on forest and environment in India. Online national webinar organized by the Department of Forestry, Government Kaktiya Post-Graduate College, Jagdalpur (Bastar), Chhattisgarh, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239945

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, September 7). Impact of COVID-19 on academic library services. One-day national webinar organized by IQAC, Library and Department of Library & Information Science, Sambhajirao Kendre Mahavidyalaya, Jalkot, Maharashtra, India, approved by Swami Ramanand Teerth Marathwada University, Nanded

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239582

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 7-8). Agricultural market reforms and market intelligence. Two-day webinar conducted by the Centre for Agricultural Market Intelligence, National Agricultural Higher Education Project (NAHEP-CAAST), Anand Agricultural University, Anand, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18240675

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 7). Natural language processing. Webinar hosted by Siddhartha Institute of Technology & Sciences in association with Pantech Solutions, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18240648

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 29–30). Forensic entomology and its relevance in legal proceedings. International webinar organized by the Department of Zoology, University of Lucknow, Lucknow, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239837

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 20). Psychological effects of COVID-19 and its solutions. Webinar organized by Bhavan's Shri A. K. Doshi Mahila College, Jamnagar, affiliated to Saurashtra University, Rajkot

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18240108

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 3–4). Advances in agricultural biotechnology. Two-day international webinar organized by the Department of Agriculture Science, AKS University, Satna, Madhya Pradesh, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239979

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 28). Online Career Summit 2020. Online career summit organized by the Career Guidance Cell (CGC), Mahlara Arts and Science College for Women, Mavoor, Kozhikode, Kerala, India (affiliated to the University of Calicut)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239930

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 28). Child rights and why they matter (Certificate of completion). UNICEF, Agora Learning Platform

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18239226

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020). Engineering project management: Scope, cost, risk and teams. Participation in an international webinar conducted on July 9, 2020, organized by the Department of Mechanical Engineering, Francis Xavier Engineering College (Autonomous), Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, India. The session was delivered by Dr. R. Sivasankaran, Assistant Professor, Thiagarajar College of Engineering, Madurai

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18240880

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 4). Designer drugs. Certificate of participation for active participation in an online lecture organized by the School of Forensic Sciences, Gujarat Forensic Sciences University, Gandhinagar, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18241036

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, July 10–11). Lessons from the past: Studying trends and responses to epidemics. Certificate of participation in a two-day national webinar organized by the Department of History, Sophia Girls' College (Autonomous), Ajmer, Rajasthan, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18241121

Nale, G. S. (2022). Certificate in Numerology (Ank Jyotish) (First Year – First Level). Awarded by Phal Jyotish Abhyas Mandal, Pune, India. (Duration: First year training completed; July 2022)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18245083

Jyotish Parichay (First Year) Certification. (2023). Jyotish Abhyas Mandal. Nashik, Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18245174

Blockchain Technology & Management (Professional Certificate). (2020). Amity Future Academy

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18245210

Astrology (Jyotish Pravin). (2022). Phal Jyotish Abhyas Mandal, Pune, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18245314

Title Health Governance, Epidemiology, and Family Law in Independent India: A Socio-Legal and Public Health Analysis within National and Global Frameworks Priyanka Jadhavar Assistant Professor, Department of Law, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar (Nale) Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, Mahendragarh, Haryana, India

Authors (2): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR; Dr.Priyanka Sambhaji Jadhavar

Published: Jan 2026 in Zenodo

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18244710

Nale, G. S. N. (2024). Post Graduate Diploma in International Relations and Security Programme. Shivaji University, Kolhapur. Faculty of Interdisciplinary Studies. (Examination passed: October 2024; Degree awarded at the 62nd Convocation, 2025)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18245029

Pariksha Pe Charcha (Certificate of Participation). (2025). Ministry of Education, Government of India. New Delhi, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18245346

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2025). Chhatrapati Shivaji Maharaj Jayanti 2025 (Certificate of appreciation for successful participation). Central University of Haryana, Mahendragarh, Haryana, India, February 19, 2025

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18245593

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2025). Synchronising elections in India: A comparative study of constitutional, federal, and democratic dimensions (Paper presentation). National Conference on One Nation, One Election: Constitutional, Federal, and Democratic Dimensions, Dr. B. R. Ambedkar National Law University, Sonipat, Haryana, India, September 6-7, 2025

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18246139

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2025). Participation in a one-day workshop on literature search skills, academic integrity, and citation for academic writing (Workshop participation). Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, Mahendergarh, Haryana, India, October 8, 2025

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18246170

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2023). Successfully completed a state-level secondary academic examination with an aggregate score of 306 out of 400, as certified by the Maharashtra State Board of Secondary and Higher Secondary Education

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18246349

Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, December 7). Visual e-quiz: Taxonomy & economic botany. Certificate of appreciation awarded for excellent performance, Department of Botany, Queen Mary's College (Autonomous), Chennai, Tamil Nadu, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18240924

Nale, G. S. (2025-2026). One-year continuous training as an Advocate-on-Record (AOR) trainee under Order IV, Rule 5 of the Supreme Court Rules, 2013. Supervised by Adv. Anil Kumar, Advocate-on-Record (AOR Code: 1649), Supreme Court of India, New Delhi. (Training commencement date officially recorded: 10 November 2025)

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18245043

Satarkar, G. S. N. (2025). The future of IPR: Trends, challenges and opportunities (Participation in two-day national conference). Maharashtra National Law University, Nagpur, India, February 7-8, 2025

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18245389

Nale, G. (2025). Understanding gender and law (BGS-011; 4-credit SWAYAM online course). Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU), New Delhi. Proctored examination held on May 17, 2025; certificate issued July 15, 2025

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18233586

Harvard Medical School. (2020). The impact of COVID-19 in pediatrics (Continuing medical education, enduring material). Harvard Medical School, Boston, MA, United States

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18236304

Satarkar, G. S. (Year). Women empowerment and social development in North India: A case study of Haryana State. Paper presented at the One Day Multidisciplinary National Conference on Republic of India: Idea and Reality, Karmaveer Hire Arts, Science, Commerce and Education College (Affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur), Gargoti, Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18230640

Nale, G. S. (2025). Participated in the international course International migration from South Asia: Context and policies. Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, India, under the Global Initiative of Academic Networks (GIAN), Ministry of Education, Government of India, April 21–25, 2025

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18234511

Nale, G. S. (2025). Participated in the two-day national conference titled The Future of IPR: Trends, Challenges and Opportunities, organized by the CIPR and DPIIT-IPR Chair at Maharashtra National Law University, Nagpur, held on February 7–8, 2025

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18233681

Nale, G. S. S. (2020). Participation in the one-day national webinar on "Contribution of Jamvani literature to Rajasthani language and literature". Jamvani Sahitya Akademi & Rajasthani Bhasha, Sahitya evam Sanskriti Akademi, Bikaner, India, November 11, 2020

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18235283

Nale, G. S. (2024). Participation in the 9th All India Shivaji University Moot Court on Alternative Dispute Resolution (ADR) and Vidhi Mela. Department of Law, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, India, March 9–10, 2024

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

Published: Jan 2026

DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18235257

Satarkar, G. N. (2020–Present). Member (Industrial Professional), All India Council for Technical Skill Development (AICTSD), India. Membership ID: AICTSD/Industrial Professional/18791

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18236477

Nale, G. S. (2023). Life Member, Institute of Constitutional and Parliamentary Studies (ICPS), New Delhi, India. Life Membership No. 1533. Approved by the Executive Council on May 16, 2023
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18233538

Nale, G. S. (2022). Certificate programme in parliamentary institutions and procedures (constitutional law). Institute of Constitutional and Parliamentary Studies (ICPS), New Delhi. Programme duration: April-July 2022; examination held October 2022; aggregate score: 83/100. Certificate issued December 19, 2022
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18233631

Nale, G. S. (2012). Diploma in information technology (Computer fundamentals, MS Office, Internet, C, C++, Java Script, MS Access, SQL Server, VB 6.0, ASP). Rashtriya Saksharta Mission IT Education, Government of India-recognized programme. Secured Grade A with 70% aggregate
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18233938

Nale, G. S. (2013). Information technology training course. The Institute of Chartered Accountants of India (ICAI), Western Regional Office, Mumbai; Pimpri Chinchwad Branch of WIRC. Certificate issued June 24, 2013 (test held June 23, 2013)
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
Published: Jan 2026
DOI: 10.5281/ZENODO.18234004

Nale, G. S. (2019). Lokshahi, nivadnuk ani suvyavasthan [Democracy, elections and good governance] (Certificate of successful completion). Law College, Phaltan, affiliated to Shivaji University, Kolhapur
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Nale, G. S. (2020). Successfully completed the professional certification course Certified Full Stack Engineer offered by Skill Sigma. The programme was conducted from May 1 to July 15, 2020, and focused on full-stack development competencies. Certificate awarded on July 18, 2020
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Nale, G. S. (2022). Awarded Second Position (Merit Rank) in the Certificate Course in Indian Constitution conducted by Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra. The merit list for the March 2022 examination was officially declared on February 1, 2023
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Mr. Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar – Empanelment as Academic Counselor for Post Graduate Certificate in Cyber Laws (PGCCL) Programme at Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU)
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Nale, G. (2021). Executive Programme—Online pre-examination test, Module 2 (Syllabus 2017). The Institute of Company Secretaries of India (ICSI), New Delhi. Course passing date: November 24, 2021
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Collection of Academic Participation and Professional Development Certificates of Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Nale Satarkar, G. S. (Year). Rashtrabhasha Prathamik Certificate (First Division). Maharashtra Rashtrabhasha Sabha, Pune, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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mR.Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar – Empanelment as Academic Counselor for Post Graduate Diploma in Criminal Justice (PGDCJ) Programme at Indira Gandhi National Open University (IGNOU)
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Collected Works and Research Articles of Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Nale, G. S. (2009). National Service Scheme (NSS) volunteer service completion certificate (2007–2009). Mahatma Phule Krishi Vidyapeeth, Rahuri, Ahmednagar, Maharashtra, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Nale Satarkar, G. S. (2020, June 6). Certificate of participation: Design thinking for health care innovation (Webinar). Department of Mechanical Engineering, SCAD College of Engineering & Technology, Tirunelveli, Tamil Nadu, India
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Integrating Intellectual Property Rights, Traditional Knowledge Systems, and the Evolution of Ayurveda: A Multidisciplinary Examination, Dr.Priyanka Jadhavar & Mr.Ganesh Nale

(Satarkar), Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences (JPharmSci), Scopus (Elsevier) Indexed, Peer-Reviewed Open Access Journal

Authors (2): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR; Dr.Priyanka Jadhavr

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An Integrated Psychological Framework of Growth, Cognition, Personality, Intelligence, Learning, and Counselling: A Holistic Approach to Human Development and Mental Health

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Evolution of Teacher Education and Educational Policy in India: Contributions of National Committees, Policy Processes, Economics of Education, and the Politics of Educational Development

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Law, Power, Belief, and Governance: An Anthropological Analysis of Legal Systems, Political Organization, Religion, and Social Change in Contemporary Societies-This research article is authored by Ganesh Shrirang Nale Satarkar, Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, Mahendragarh, Haryana, India, and Dr. Priyanka Sambhaji Jadhavar, Assistant Professor, Department of Law, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India

Authors (2): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR; Sambhaji Jadhavar Dr. Priyanka

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Anthropology as a Scientific Discipline: Epistemological Foundations, Methodological Traditions, and Interdisciplinary Perspectives in Social Research- authored by Dr. Priyanka Sambhaji Jadhavar, Assistant Professor, Department of Law, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India, and Ganesh Shrirang Nale Satarkar, Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, Mahendragarh, Haryana, India

Authors (2): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR; Sambhaji Jadhavar Dr. Priyanka

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Culture, Society, and Economy: A Holistic Anthropological Analysis of Social Institutions, Kinship, and Economic Life - authored by Ganesh Shrirang Nale Satarkar, Research Scholar, Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, Mahendragarh, Haryana, India,

Authors (2): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR; Sambhaji Jadhavar Dr. Priyanka

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From Evolutionism to Postmodernism: A Critical Synthesis of Major Theoretical Traditions in Social Anthropology- article is authored by Ganesh Shrirang Nale Satarkar, Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, Mahendragarh, Haryana, India, and Dr. Priyanka Sambhaji Jadhavar, Assistant Professor, Department of Law, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India

Authors (2): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR; Sambhaji Jadhavar Dr. Priyanka

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Title of the Article Integrated Clinical, Surgical, Endocrine, Oncological, Gastrointestinal, and Criminal Justice Perspectives in Medical and Legal Practice Authors and Affiliations Ganesh Shrirang Nale Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, Mahendragarh, Haryana, India Dr. Priyanka Sambhaji Jadhavar Assistant Professor, Department of Law, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India

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Title of the Article Surgery, Law, Methods and Surgical Skills: An Integrated Four-Pillar Framework for Contemporary Surgical Practice Authors and Affiliations Dr. Priyanka Sambhaji Jadhavar Assistant Professor, Department of Law, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India Ganesh Shrirang Nale Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, Mahendragarh, Haryana, India

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India's Environmental Legal and Policy Framework: From Pollution Control to Sustainable Development and Environmental Justice Authors and Affiliations Dr. Priyanka Sambhaji Jadhavar Assistant Professor, Department of Law Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India Ganesh Shrirang Nale Department of Sociology Central University of Haryana, Mahendragarh, Haryana, India

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Law, Medicine, and Forensic Science: A Comprehensive Medico-Legal Analysis of Ethics, Liability, Mental Health, Reproductive Technologies, and Medical Negligence Ganesh Shrirang Nale (Central University of Haryana) & Dr. Priyanka Sambhaji Jadhavar (Shivaji University, Kolhapur)

Authors (2): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR; Sambhaji Jadhavar Dr. Priyanka

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Medicine, Surgery, and Law: A Medico-Legal Analysis of Healthcare Systems, Clinical Practice, and Institutional Accountability in India Authors and Affiliations Dr. Priyanka Sambhaji Jadhavar Assistant Professor, Department of Law Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India Ganesh Shrirang Nale Department of Sociology Central University of Haryana, Mahendragarh, Haryana, India

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Comparative Constitutionalism in Germany and France: A Study of Democratic Governance, Fundamental Rights, and Constitutional Design Authors and Affiliations Ganesh Shrirang Nale Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, Mahendragarh, Haryana, India Dr. Priyanka Sambhaji Jadhavar Assistant Professor, Department of Law, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India

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Title of the Article Constitutionalism and Democratic Governance in South Asia: A Comparative Study of the Constitutions of Sri Lanka and Bangladesh Authors and Affiliations Dr. Priyanka Sambhaji Jadhavar Assistant Professor, Department of Law Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India Ganesh Shrirang Nale Department of Sociology Central University of Haryana, Mahendragarh, Haryana, India

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Title of the Article Vocational Education, Skill Development, and Lifelong Learning in India: From Workforce Preparation to the Vision of a Learning Society Authors and Affiliations Dr. Priyanka Sambhaji Jadhavar¹ ¹ Assistant Professor, Department of Law, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India Ganesh Shrirang Nale² ² Department of Sociology,

Authors (2): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR; Sambhaji Jadhavar Dr. Priyanka

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Tradition, Transformation, and Continuity: Cultural Concepts, Historiography, and Symbolic Change in Indian and Global Contexts Authors and Affiliations Ganesh Shrirang Nale Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana Dr. Priyanka Sambhaji Jadhavar Assistant Professor, Department of Law, Shivaji University

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Constitutional Evolution, Human Rights, and Democratic Sovereignty: A Comparative Analysis of France and Germany from 1791 to 2025- Ganesh Nale Department of Law Shivaji University, Kolhapur Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Breaking Cycles of Injustice: Community-Based Interventions for Gender, Youth, and Restorative Justice in India- Mr. Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar Affiliation Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Reimagining Transparency in the Digital Age: The Right to Information Act, 2005 and the Challenges of AI, ICT, and E-Governance- Mr. Ganesh Shrirang Nale Satarkar M.A. Sociology (2nd Year) Department of Sociology Affiliation Central University of Haryana, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Constitutionalism across Political Systems: A Comparative Study of the United States Constitution and the Constitution of the People's Republic of China -Nale Ganesh Affiliation Department of Law, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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The Digital Economy Beyond Borders: Towards Harmonized Competition and Consumer Protection Regimes Author Mr. Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar Author Affiliation M.A. Sociology Central University of Haryana Mahendragarh, Haryana, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Revisiting India's Republic at 75: Postcolonial Narratives, Democratic Diversity, Federal Challenges, and Constitutional Pathways in Disaster Management- Mr. Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar Affiliation Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Ensuring Safe and Quality Food in India: A Comprehensive Review of Food Laws, Regulations, and Standards -Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar (Nale) Affiliation Central University of Haryana, India Corresponding Author Email: ganeshnale0@gmail.com

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Evolving Dimensions of Law and Justice: Navigating Rights, Accountability, Technology, and Environmental Challenges in the 21st Century I had the honor of presenting my research paper at the Rajiv Gandhi School of Intellectual Property Law (RGSOIPL), Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Kharagpur, at the All India level. I am delighted to share that my paper has been successfully published in a peer-reviewed journal today

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Comparative Constitutionalism: A Systematic Analysis of the United States Constitution and the United Kingdom's Uncodified Constitutional Framework- Codified Supremacy and Parliamentary Sovereignty: A Comparative Study of US and UK Constitutional Models Nale Ganesh Department of Law, Shivaji University, Kolhapur, Maharashtra, India Short Creative Title: Two Democracies, Two Constitutional Paths

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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Forensic Medicine and Medical Jurisprudence in India" published in the Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences (Scopus Indexed), authored by Ganesh Nale, Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Maratha Reservation: A Sociological Study of Social, Economic and Political Factors- This paper, authored by Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar (Nale), Roll No. 240322, MA in Sociology – II (Academic Year 2025–2026), Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, India, with Co-Author Dr. Yudhvir, Assistant Professor, Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, offers a comprehensive sociological analysis of the Maratha reservation movement in Maharashtra

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Regulating Artificial Intelligence in India: Legal Frameworks, Governance Challenges, and the Path Toward a Dedicated AI Law- This research paper, authored by Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar Nale, Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, India

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Sociology of Knowledge: Understanding the Interconnections of Science, Technology and Power - Ganesh Shrirang Nale Department of Sociology, Central University of Haryana, India Discipline: Sociology, Sociology of Knowledge, Science–Technology–Society (STS), Epistemology

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Victimology in Global and Indian Perspectives: Evolution, Impact, Legal Frameworks, and Contemporary Developments

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Victimology in Global and Indian Perspectives: Evolution, Impact, Legal Frameworks, and Contemporary Developments

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The Structure and Dynamics of Social Institutions: A Sociological Study of Marriage, Family, Economy, Polity, Religion, Education, Law, and Customs

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Constitutional Morality and the Crisis of Political Accountability: A Critical Study of the 130th Amendment Bill, 2025 in Strengthening Indian Democracy

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Industrial Relations and Trade Unions in India: Concepts, Evolution, Approaches, and Emerging Challenges in a Changing Industrial Landscape- (UGC-CARE Group II, Scopus Indexed)

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Pioneering Women Lawyers and Women Judges of the Supreme Court of India: A Comprehensive Study of Historical Struggles, Career Trajectories, Jurisprudential Contributions, and Gendered Barriers in Indian Constitutional Justice

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Cyber Security and Artificial Intelligence in the Digital Age: Legal, Ethical, and Societal Perspectives – Journal of Technology (UGC-CARE Group II, Scopus Indexed) by Ganesh S. Satarkar & Dr. Priyanka S. Jadhavar

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Biofertilizers and Bioagents in Indian Agriculture: Scientific Mechanisms, Quality Standards and Legal Regulatory Framework

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Dr. B. R. Ambedkar and the Global Quest for Labour Rights: A Vision of Social and Economic Democracy," authored by Mr. Ganesh Shrirang Satarkar (M.A. Sociology, Central University of Haryana), is published in the Worldwide International Inter Disciplinary Research Journal (WIIDRJ), Vol. I, Issue CXXXVIII, dated 4-5 December 2025

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Integrating Indian Knowledge Systems with Contemporary Psychology: A Comparative Interdisciplinary Analysis of Mind, Behaviour, Health, and Human Development

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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Evolving Dimensions of Labour Legislation in India: A Study of Objectives, Principles, and Legal Frameworks for Social Justice

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Cyber Security and Artificial Intelligence in the Digital Age: Legal, Ethical, and Societal Perspectives – Journal of Technology (UGC-CARE Group II, Scopus Indexed) by Ganesh S. Satarkar & Dr. Priyanka S. Jadhavar

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Evolving Paradigms of Criminological Thought: A Comparative and Integrative Analysis of Social Control, Conflict, Modern, and Contemporary Theories

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Reimagining Privacy in the Age of Artificial Intelligence: A Socio-Legal Analysis of India's Digital Personal Data Protection Act, 2023

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Data Sovereignty and Copyright Governance in the Digital Age: A Legal Pathway Towards Viksit Bharat 2047

Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR

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SCHOOLS OF CRIMINOLOGY: EVOLUTION, THEORIES, AND CONTEMPORARY PERSPECTIVES BY - MR. GANESH SHRIRANG NALE (SATARKAR)

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Synchronising Elections in India: A Comparative Study of Constitutional, Federal and Democratic Challenges
Authors (1): GANESH SHRIRANG SATARKAR
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The Indian Criminal Procedure Code (CrPC) - 1973 Under Section 293: Reports of Government Scientific Experts
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